

SIMULATION OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY FOR TITANIUM BORIDE PARTICLE DISPERSED ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Titanium diboride (TiB₂) particle dispersed pure aluminum (Al) composites with different microstructure and dispersibility of particles was fabricated by spark plasma sintering process. Dispersibility of TiB₂ particles in composites was estimated quantitatively by localized number in 2 dimension method (LN2DRver). Then, the measured thermal conductivity of 10vol. % TiB₂/aluminum composites with different dispersibility was corrected by the difference of the density, but the obvious effect of the dispersibility of particles on thermal conductivity was not observed. Then, the effect of the dispersibility of particles on the thermal conductivity in composites with various volume fraction and size of particles was estimated by simulation. The change of the thermal conductivity for dispersibility was very small. On the other hand, as decreasing the particle size, the thermal conductivity was decreased obviously, and this tendency is enhanced by increasing a volume fraction of particles.

1 INTRODUCTION

As pure aluminum (Al) has been used for the electrical wiring, power cable, heat sink, heat exchanger and so on because of light weight, good thermal and electrical conductivity. On the other hand, the utilization of heat sink and electrical conducting materials used in severe environment such as wide range temperature has been requiring recently because of the higher integration and higher power semi-conductor and the development of new semiconductor such as SiC, GaAs and diamond. Unfortunately, pure Al block has low mechanical properties at high temperature and has higher thermal expansion compared with semiconductors. In this study, the development of titanium diboride particle dispersed pure Al composites (TiB₂/ Al composites) with high thermal conductivity, low thermal expansion and good mechanical properties at high temperature was attempted. Because, TiB₂ has good thermal conductivity with 66.4 W/mK and low thermal expansion with $3.7 \times 10^{-6}/K$, low density with 4.5g/cm³. Furthermore, as TiB₂ do not react with Al, and has good wettability for molten Al, the development of TiB₂/ Al composites is expected to have high performance. As commercial TiB₂ is usually supplied as uniaxial crystal particles with several micro meter in average diameter. The composites is expected to have good mechanical properties with equivalent properties because of orowan mechanism. But the properties of the composites seems to be affected by the size, volume fraction and dispersibility of the particles. Therefore, it is important to clarify the effect of these factors on properties. In this study, the morphology such as particle size and distribution on thermal conductivity for composites was investigated by using experiments and simulation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Starting materials used are pure Al powders with 3 μm in average diameter and 99.9% in purity, and TiB₂ powders with average diameter 2.62 μm (Japan New Metals Co., Ltd.). 10 vol. % TiB₂ particle containing Al powder were mixed in ethanol (wet blending) or in air (dry blending) with alumina ball in V shape type mixer. Mixed powder was sintered by spark plasma sintering (SPS) with 500 MPa in applied pressure, 793-873 K in temperature in order to obtain TiB₂ particle dispersed Al matrix composites. The density of the composites was measured by the Archimedes method, and the microstructure was observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The dispersibility of the TiB₂ particles in composites was evaluated quantitatively by localized number in 2 dimension method (LN2DRver) [1] and SEM image. LN2DRver is defined as the number of bary center of particle included in measuring circle as shown in fig. 1, which is defined by following equation.

$$\frac{7}{\pi R_{2D}^2} = \lambda_A \Rightarrow R_{2D} = \left(\frac{7}{\pi \lambda_A} \right)^{1/2} = \frac{1.493}{\lambda_A^{1/2}}$$

Hence, R_{2D} : radius of the measuring circle, λ_A : number density.

Fig. 1 Ordered and random arrangements of gravity center of particles, (a) the closet hexagonal and (b) a random arrangement in 2-dimesion.

The theoretical LN2DRver value of 10 vol. % TiB₂ /Al for uniform distribution of particles for LN2DRver is 4.5 as shown in fig. 2. As increasing clustering behavior, this value is increasing. The thermal conductivity was measured by steady state method. Then, the effect of thermal heat transfer at TiB₂ /Al interface on the thermal conductivity of the composites was estimated by simulating the effect of TiB₂ particle size on thermal conductivity.

Fig. 2 Relationship between LN2DRver and volume fraction of TiB₂ for iB₂/Al composite.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows the microstructure of 10 vol. % TiB₂ / Al composites prepared by using wet and dry blending for powder mixing. It seems TiB₂ particles distributed uniformly, but there is some difference for particle density by a place and some aggregation areas are observed. But the obvious difference of the distribution and aggregation for particles is not clear. Therefore, LN2DR_{var} was measured from twenty SEM images for each composites. Table 1 shows LN2DR_{var} and average particle size of 10 vol. % TiB₂ /Al composites prepared by wet and dry blending for powder mixing. LN2DR_{var} of the composites with wet and dry processes was 12.83 and 13.05, respectively. LN2DR_{var} of wet blending was lower than that of dry blending. It means the dispersibility of the particles in wet blending composites is better than the dry blending. In wet blending, As it seems the aggregation of as-received TiB₂ particles disappeared by wet blending, the dispersibility was improved compared with dry blending. On the other hand, average particle size of the composites by wet and dry blending was 1.27 μm and 1.16 μm, respectively. Particle size of wet blending was larger than dry blending, which is caused by the soft blend for wet blending.

Fig.3 Microstructure of 10 vol. % TiB₂ / Al composites prepared by using (a) wet and (b) dry blending for powder mixing observed by SEM.

Table 1 LN2DR_{var} and average particle size of 10 vol. % TiB₂ /Al composites prepared by wet and dry blending for powder mixing.

	LN2DR _{var}	Particle size [μm]
Wet blending	12.83	1.27
Dry blending	13.05	1.16

Table 2 show the thermal conductivity and relative density for the composites prepared by wet and dry blending. The composites prepared by dry blending has higher thermal conductivity than wet blending, but has higher relative density than wet blending. The thermal conductivity was corrected by the equation suggested by B. Nati-Ali [2] as bellow, which is the model considering the influence of the density.

$$4\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_p(3v_p - 1) + \lambda_c(3v_c - 1) + \left[\{ \lambda_p(3v_p - 1) + \lambda_c(3v_c - 1) \}^2 + 8\lambda_p\lambda_c \right]^{1/2}$$

Hence, λ_p , λ_c , v_p , and v_c are thermal conductivity of pores, thermal conductivity of composites, porosity and relative density of composites, respectively.

Then the corrected by the equation suggested by L. C. Davis [3] as bellow, which is the model considering the influence of the particle size.

$$\frac{K}{K_m} = \frac{[K_p(1 + 2\alpha) + 2K_m] + 2\phi[K_p(1 - \alpha) - K_m]}{[K_p(1 + 2\alpha) + 2K_m] - \phi[K_p(1 - \alpha) - K_m]}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{R_{bd}K_m}{a}$$

Hence, K_m , K_p , ϕ , R_{bd} and α are thermal conductivity of pure Al, thermal conductivity of TiB_2 , volume fraction, interfacial thermal resistance and radius of particle, respectively. Thermal conductivity of pure Al and TiB_2 used was measured and was obtained from catalog values, respectively.

Corrected value of the thermal conductivity for 10 vol. % TiB_2 /Al composites prepared by wet and dry blending are 156W/mK and 155W/mK, respectively. The results shows two composites had almost same thermal conductivity, and it seems the effect of dispersibility of TiB_2 particles is small.

Table 2 Thermal conductivity obtained by experiment, relative density and corrected thermal conductivity by relative density for 10 vol. % TiB_2 / Al composites prepared by wet and dry blending for powder mixing.

	Thermal conductivity (Experimental) [W/(m·K)]	Relative density [%]	Corrected thermal conductivity by relative density [W/(m·K)]
Wet blending	147	94.8	156
Dry blending	155	98.3	155

Then, how the effect of the dispersibility on the thermal conductivity was analyzed by simulation. Fig. 4 shows the result of the computer simulation for the relationship between LN2DRvar and TiB_2 particle distributions in composite microstructure. As increasing LN2DRvar, the degree of aggregation increased. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between LN2DRvar and thermal conductivity for 10 vol. % TiB_2 / Al composites. As increasing LN2DRvar, the thermal conductivity improved, but its degree was very small. And it seems that the effect of dispersibility on the thermal conductivity is small because of the small difference of LN2DRver for wet and dry process.

Usually, thermal transfer between dissimilar materials degrade the thermal conductivity in composites because of the lower heat transfer coefficient. Therefore, it seems the composites with smaller particle size has lower thermal conductivity than the composite with larger particle size because of the difference of interface density for dissimilar materials.

Fig. 4 The relationship between LN2DRvar and TiB₂ particle distributions in composites.

Fig. 5 Effect of LN2DRvar on thermal conductivity for 10 vol. % TiB₂ / Al composites calculated by simulation.

Fig. 6 shows the effect of particle size (element size) on thermal conductivity for TiB₂ / Al composites as a function of volume fraction of TiB₂ particles, which was calculated by theoretical model. As decreasing TiB₂ particle size, the effective thermal conductivity decreased. As the threshold of particle size was calculated as 0.48 μm, which is obtained from phonon diffuse mismatch model, it seems the effect of particle size is impossible to ignore. But average particle size by wet and dry process is almost same in this study, it seems that the obvious difference of thermal conductivity was not measured.

Fig. 6 Effect of particle size (element size) on thermal conductivity for TiB₂ / Al composites as a function of volume fraction of TiB₂ particles, which is obtained by simulation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In order to clarify the effect of particle dispersion on thermal conductivity for TiB₂ particle dispersed Al composite, the composites with different dispersibility of particles was fabricated by spark plasma sintering with different powder mixing method of TiB₂ and Al particles by dry mixing and wet mixing in ethanol by ball milling. Following is our results.

1. Dispersibility of particles in 10vol. % TiB₂ /Al composites by dry and wet mixing was estimated by LN2DRver method. The quantitative difference of dispersibility was performed as 12.83 and 13.05 for LN2DRver value, respectively.
2. The difference of thermal conductivity of the composites by dispersibility was not able to be estimated from experimental result, which is caused by the small change.
3. By using computer simulation for the estimation of thermal conductivity of the composites, the difference of the thermal conductivity for the dispersibility and size of the particles was estimated. The change of the thermal conductivity for the dispersibility was very small. On the other hand, the difference of the thermal conductivity for the particle size is relatively large, and the degree of change increased as increasing volume fraction of the composites.

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